

A FAST UNCERTAINTY QUANTIFICATION METHOD FOR FAILURE PREDICTION OF LARGE COMPOSITE STRUCTURAL ELEMENTS

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ABSTRACT

Composite materials are widely adopted in civil aircraft, as they contribute to lightweight, strong structures and offer the possibility of innovative structural concepts. However, traditional and empirical tools are often inadequate for evaluating such novel designs in the early stages of development, limiting the exploration of their full potential. To address this limitation, fast prediction models are needed to efficiently explore the design space. A key challenge in modelling large composite structures is the curse of dimensionality caused by detailed laminate stacking sequences, which greatly increases the demand for training data and computational resources. In this study, we propose a fast uncertainty quantification (UQ) model for predicting failure in composite wing boxes using Bayesian Neural Networks. The model predicts the mean failure response across various wing box geometries while quantifying the influence of different composite layups with stochastic terms. We focus on a novel structural concept, a Z-beam wing box, which is designed to achieve favourable bending–torsion coupling. Unit cells of the Z-beam structure are simulated under periodic boundary conditions. Failure indices are computed using refined local models at stress concentrations, based on the LaRC05 failure criterion. A diverse set of geometries and layups is sampled to train the UQ model. Results show that the proposed approach can accurately and quickly predict the probability distributions of failure indices for different wing box designs under varying load conditions. The predicted bounds of maximum failure indices provide valuable insights for structural assessment and highlight the need for further layup optimization when necessary.

1 INTRODUCTION

Europe’s aviation sector has launched the “Destination 2050” initiative, aiming for net-zero emissions in aviation by mid-century [1]. One key strategy is increasing the wing aspect ratio to reduce induced drag [2]. For instance, Boeing’s 777-X incorporates folding wingtips to extend wingspan [3]. Similarly, Airbus’ ZEROe program [4] and the University of Bristol’s Ultra-Green Wing (BUG) project [5], among others, are investigating the opportunities and challenges associated with high-aspect-ratio wings (HARW) [2]. A primary challenge lies in the significant structural weight increase associated with higher aspect ratios [6].

Aeroelastic tailoring has emerged as a promising passive technique to enhance both aerodynamic and structural performance [7]. Stodieck [8 and Airbus 9] introduced a Z-beam structural concept designed to improve aeroelastic tailoring, especially in reducing maneuver and gust loads. This approach shows potential in overcoming the aeroelastic limitations of HARW designs. As illustrated in Figure 1, the black lines represent the wing box spars and ribs, the grey lines indicate stringers, and the red lines highlight the Z-beams.

Figure 1: Z-beam structures in the wing tip region of BUG wing, and the hotspot for failure

This paper proposes an uncertainty quantification framework based on Bayesian neural networks for rapid prediction of novel wing structures. The Z-beam concept is selected as a representative case study. To model the behaviour of the Z-beam wing box at the wing tip, the structure is divided into multiple repeating unit cells, as illustrated in Figure 1. Each unit cell is analysed under periodic boundary conditions to capture its response to tension, bending, and torsion. Following this, the primary failure hotspot within the composite structure is identified. A refined local model is then developed for detailed failure analysis at this critical region.

2 PARAMETRIC MODELLING AND COMPUTATIONAL METHODS

2.1 Parameters of the Z-beam Unit Cell

The Z-beam unit cell comprises the upper and lower cover skins, front and rear C-shaped spars, a zigzag I-shaped beam, and titanium bolts. The bolts are made from aerospace-grade Ti-6Al-4V, while all other components use IM7/8551-7 carbon/epoxy composite. For simplicity, the design is parameterized using three independent geometric variables ($\Theta = [t_{\text{spar}}, t_{\text{beam}}, \alpha_{\text{beam}}]$), as illustrated in Figure 2. The definitions and ranges of these parameters are provided in Table 1. It is important to note that the spanwise length (L_z in mm) is a function of the beam angle α_{beam} .

The composite layup configuration of the wing box components is denoted by Γ , which encodes the ply orientation angles for all layers across all structural components. As a result, Γ is a high-dimensional parameter, because there are often hundreds of plies in laminates for large structures. Additionally, its dimensionality varies with laminate thickness, as different components may have different numbers of plies. These characteristics make modeling Γ particularly challenging for fast prediction models.

In this study, the geometric parameters are uniformly sampled within the ranges specified in Table 1 to generate a training dataset. For each wing box geometry, composite layups for the spars and Z-beam are then sampled. To ensure design feasibility, the layups are selected from a predefined set of candidate configurations. The front and rear spars share the same layup, while the cover skin layup is fixed to nominal values throughout this work.

Figure 2: Geometric parameters of the Z-beam unit cell model [10]

Variable	Meaning	Range
t_{spar} (mm)	thickness of spar	[5, 25]
t_{beam} (mm)	thickness of beam	[10, 22]
α_{beam} (°)	angle between diagonal member of the beam and the spar	[20, 60]

Table 1: Independent geometric parameters

2.2 Finite Element Models

The training data for machine learning is obtained from multiscale simulations; the simulation process is shown in Figure 3. Abaqus is used as the numerical solver in this work. The behaviour of the complete zigzag beam in the wing tip region of BUG wing, as shown in Figure 1, is approximated by Z-beam unit cells arranged in a one-dimensional series. The aeroelastic deformation of the full wing box can be simulated by reduced order models [11], which only requires the homogenized stiffness matrix of each unit cell:

$$\begin{bmatrix} F_z \\ M_z \\ M_x \\ M_y \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} C_{11} & C_{12} & C_{13} & C_{14} \\ C_{21} & C_{22} & C_{23} & C_{24} \\ C_{31} & C_{32} & C_{33} & C_{34} \\ C_{41} & C_{42} & C_{43} & C_{44} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_z \\ \kappa_z \\ \kappa_x \\ \kappa_y \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

At the structural element level, the loads (Δ) applied on the unit cell model include the axial strain in z-axis (ϵ_z), twist rate about z-axis (κ_z , rad/mm), and the curvature about x/y-axis (κ_x, κ_y , 1/mm). The loads are employed using periodic boundary conditions (PBCs), and the displacement boundaries (\mathbf{u}) around failure hotspots are determined.

At the hotspot level, stress ($\boldsymbol{\sigma}$) and strain ($\boldsymbol{\epsilon}$) fields are assessed on a finer mesh using a global-local approach. Then, failure indices (FIs, \mathbf{v}) are calculated using the LaRC05 failure criteria [13]. By analysing various strain states, a failure index map is generated by identifying the maximum failure index within the structure. Consequently, the failure envelop can be obtained from the FI map. The details can be found in [10,14] and are therefore not repeated here.

Figure 3: Multiscale simulation of composite Z-beam wing box elements

3 MACHINE LEARNING FOR Z-BEAM WING BOXES

3.1 Database

There are 1400 valid unit cell samples in the database. The homogenized stiffness matrix $[C]$ and mass matrix $[M]$ are extracted. Figure 4 shows the relationship between the stiffness components with geometry parameters, when the composite layup are set to nominal values. It shows that t_{spar} dominates C_{11}, C_{33}, C_{13} ; t_{beam} dominates C_{23} ; t_{spar} and t_{beam} have same level of influence on C_{22} .

Figure 4: Distribution of stiffness components in the database

3.2 A Machine Learning Model for Z-beam Unit Cell's properties

A machine learning model is used to predict the properties of Z-beam unit cell that are independent of the loads, i.e., the weight and homogenized stiffness matrix. The model input is the geometric parameters Θ and superlayer parameters ($\Omega = [r_{0,\text{beam}}, r_{90,\text{beam}}, r_{0,\text{spar}}, r_{90,\text{spar}}]$), the output is the weight (w) and the homogenised stiffness matrix ($[C]$), as shown in Figure 5. The superlayer parameters, i.e., percentage of plies in the beam and spar are used to predict the homogenised stiffness. It is because the structure dimension (i.e., wing box height) is much larger than the laminate thickness, consequently, the stacking sequence details have insignificant influence on $[C]$.

A simple artificial neural network (ANN) is employed, which contains three hidden layers with 512 neurons. The loss function is the mean square error (MSE) between the predicted values and the real values. The initial learning rate is 0.001 for 500 epochs. Adam optimizer[15] is used for training. 20 samples are randomly selected for testing. Figure 6 shows the prediction error on the training set and testing set during training. It shows that the model can achieve a good prediction accuracy.

Figure 5: ANN for the prediction of weight and stiffness

Figure 6: Prediction error on the training set and testing set during training.

3.3 Bayesian Neural Networks for Failure Prediction

Bayesian neural networks are trained on the wing box database. The loss function is the evidence lower bounds (ELBO) on the training set. The initial learning rate is 0.001 for 2,000 epochs. Adam optimizer is again used for training. Figure 7 presents a predicted maximum failure index map of a Z-beam geometry. The details of the proposed uncertainty quantification model and more results will be presented in the conference.

Figure 7: The expected maximum failure index map of a Z-beam wing box geometry. The wing box is under bending strains (κ_x) and torsional strains (κ_z), the geometric parameters are $t_{spar} = 19$, $t_{beam} = 19$, $\alpha_{beam} = 50^\circ$. The solid red line shows the expected failure envelop ($\mu(FI) = 1$), the orange and blue dashed lines show the upper and lower bounds of FI (or 1σ confidence interval). The black dashed lines show the failure envelop of the wing box geometry with the nominal layup.

3 CONCLUSIONS

The Z-beam structure enables tailored bending–torsion coupling through geometric modifications, making it well-suited for high aspect ratio wing applications. A simple neural network is trained to predict the homogenized stiffness of the Z-beam unit cell, enabling fast and accurate evaluations for preliminary design. To assess structural reliability, an uncertainty quantification model is developed and trained to predict failure behavior and capture the influence of composite layup variations. Results demonstrate that the proposed method can efficiently and accurately predict the probability distributions of failure indices across different wing box configurations under varying loading conditions. This

approach is therefore well-suited for early-stage design and evaluation of novel composite wing concepts.

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